

Sports Selection as A Means of Identifying Prospective Young Athletes (Rugby)

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of staged sports selection for everyone involved in sports activities. The article deals with the stages of sports selection and analysis of the activities of athletes of rugby players. In conclusion, conclusions are drawn.

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Sports selection is a set of measures to identify athletes, with a high level of ability, meeting the requirements of the specifics of the sport. Qualitatively changing, selection is included in the system of long-term training. The choice of a sport by each person, to the greatest extent corresponding to his individual characteristics, is the essence of sports orientation. Sports orientation is associated, first of all, with children and youth and mass sports. A well-defined sporting orientation increases the efficiency of sport selection.

Sports selection in the process of long-term training - purposeful long-term training and education of high-class athletes is a complex process, the quality of which is determined by a number of factors. One of these factors is the selection of gifted children and adolescents, their sports orientation. Pedagogical methods allow us to assess the level of development of physical qualities, coordination abilities and sports and technical skills of young athletes. In modern society, the problem of effective use of the potential of human abilities is increasingly being put on the agenda. One of these factors is the selection of gifted children and adolescents, their sports orientation. Sports selection is a set of measures to identify athletes, with a high level of abilities that meet the requirements of the specifics of the sport.

Sports orientation is a system of organizational and methodological measures, allowing to outline the direction of specialization of a young athlete in a particular sport. Sports orientation is based on an assessment of the capabilities of a particular person, on the basis of which the choice of the most suitable sports activity is made. To choose a type of sports activity for each person involved is a task of sports orientation; to select the most suitable, based on the requirements of the sport, is the task of sports selection. A wide variety of sports expands the individual's ability to achieve mastery in one of the sports activities. Weak manifestation of personality traits and qualitative abilities in relation to one of the sports cannot be regarded as a lack of athletic ability. Less preferred traits in one type of sports activity may be favorable factors and provide high performance in a different way. In this regard, the prediction of sports abilities can be carried out only in relation to a particular species or a group of species, based on the general provisions characteristic of the selection system. Sports selection begins in childhood and ends in the national teams of the country to participate in the Olympic Games. It is carried out in four stages.

At the first stage of selection, a massive screening of the contingents of children 6-10 years old is carried out with the aim of orienting them towards engaging in this or that kind of sport. Children are admitted to the primary training groups of children's and youth sports schools (CYSS) in accordance with their age, specific to the sport. The criteria for sports orientation are the recommendations of a physical education teacher, medical examination data, anthropometric measurements and their assessment from a perspective.

At the second stage of selection, athletic gifted schoolchildren are identified for recruiting educational and training groups and groups of sports improvement of the CYSS, SDYUSSH. The selection is carried out during the last year of study in groups of initial training according to the following program: health assessment; compliance with control and transfer standards, designed for each sport; anthropometric measurements; identification of the growth rates of physical qualities and sports results. Pedagogical control tests (tests) make it possible to judge the presence of the necessary physical qualities and abilities of an individual for successful specialization in a particular sport. Among the physical qualities and abilities there are conservative, genetically determined qualities and abilities, which are very

difficult to develop and improve in the process of training. These include speed, relative strength, some anthropometric indicators (structure and proportions of the body), способность к максимальному потреблению кислорода, economical functioning of the autonomic systems of the body, some mental characteristics of the personality. These physical qualities and abilities have an important predictive value in the selection of children and adolescents to educational and training groups.

Psychological examinations allow us to assess the manifestation of such qualities, as activity and perseverance in wrestling, independence, dedication, sports hard work, the ability to mobilize during the competition, reaction to an unsuccessful performance in it, activity and perseverance in wrestling.

At the third stage of sports selection in order to find promising athletes and enroll them in Olympic training centers, Sports school is a survey of the competitive activity of athletes with an expert assessment and with their subsequent testing during the republican competitions for junior youth groups, those. at the age when sports improvement groups are completed.

At the fourth stage of the sports selection, viewing training camps should be held in each Olympic sport. The selection is carried out according to the following indicators: 1) sports and technical results and their dynamics (beginning, peak, decline) by years of training; 2) the degree of consolidation of the technique of performing the most unstable elements when performing an exercise in extreme conditions; 3) the degree of technical readiness and resistance of the athlete to confounding factors. During this stage of the sports selection of candidates, the following components are taken into account: the level of special physical fitness; level of sports and technical readiness; level of tactical readiness; the level of mental readiness; health status.

The final decision on attracting children to engage in a particular sport should be based on a comprehensive assessment of all the listed data, and not on the account of any one or two indicators. The selection process is closely related to the stages of sports training and the characteristics of the sport (age at the beginning of classes, classification standards, etc.) the quality of selection is an important condition for the success of long-term training of sports reserves. For each candidate, selection ultimately boils down to a positive or negative result. A positive selection result can, for example, to be enrolled in a group and a team, the inclusion of a substitute

athlete in the game, appointing a coach, and the negative one is realized in the form of a deduction, exclusion, removal, disqualification, transfer of the main athlete to the number of substitutes, etc.

A characteristic feature of modern sports is the search for talented youth, organization of scientifically grounded sports orientation. Competitive activity of players of various roles of the rugby team differs in great variety and specificity. During the match, the player is required to perform many technical actions, such as: ball handling technique (transfer, reception, selection, catching, kick), fraudulent actions (feints), protection from capture or capture. Analysis of the activities of rugby players shows, that even in the lines of attack, the functions of the players sometimes do not coincide.

Based on the study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. For sports selection in rugby such a feature is characteristic, as the need to take into account a significant set of factors. The activities of representatives of different game roles can present a variety of requirements during the match. To the indicators, determining the technical readiness of rugby players, include: an arsenal of techniques used in

gaming activities; reliability as the success of their implementation under conditions of competitive stress; the optimal solution by the player to the tasks of the tactical moment. Weight and height indicators in combination with a certain level of development of physical qualities are no less important. The most massive and strong are the forwards, of which the second row players are the tallest; for midfielders, length and weight are not important (usually they are of average height), but the requirements for their speed and coordination are high, as well as tactical thinking; defenders tend to with a height above average, they must have excellent speed data simultaneously with the accuracy of passing and hitting the ball. One of the important components of selection in rugby is to identify the most technically and physically prepared players in accordance with the specified requirements.

2. There are a number of criteria for the effectiveness of a player's performance of his role during a match. The scrum players (attackers) need successful actions when performing a capture in defense and contact actions in an attack; the main job of number 9 is a pass from the ground, and this is a very complex technical action, as the pass must be accurate and fast; The 10th number must tactically competently kick and also own the pass, to pass the ball to your center players, without slowing down the attack; center-backs - 12 and 13 - must grapple well enough, like scrum players, and play

reliably in contact; the wingers - 11 and 14 - must have good catch, excellent feints, since they are the ones that complete most of the fan's attacks, and they often have to outplay their opponents.

3. It is important to timely identify the predisposition of a young rugby player to a particular playing function. This will give him the opportunity to fully realize himself as an athlete, develop and demonstrate in the best possible way their inclinations. In turn, the performance of activities to which the player is predisposed, will save it from stress, which means it will preserve the highest achievements for sports. It is advisable, before reaching the age of 15-16, to obtain the most complete information about the predisposition to one or another activity during the match, to a certain role and playing style, since by this age the player's central nervous system finishes forming.

All of the above factors must be taken into account when conducting sports selection events with the aim of recruiting youth rugby teams.

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